

Effect of organic and inorganic fertilizers on the yield response of RED AMARANTH (AMARANTHUS CURENTUS)

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ABSTRACT

As a test crop red amaranth was selected to determine the effects of organic and inorganic fertilizers on the yield response. Eight treatments were conducted in the experiment viz. no fertilizer or manure (control); poultry manure; city waste; poultry manure in combination with inorganic N, P, K (NPK) fertilizer; city waste in combination with inorganic NPK fertilizer and cow dung in combination with inorganic NPK fertilizer and only inorganic N, P, K fertilizer. Morphological attributes (plant height, no. of leaves per plant, largest leaf length, largest leaf breadth, shoot breadth, shoot length, root length, yield per plot) and physiological attributes (fresh weight per plant, dry weight per plant, moisture content, dry matter content) of amaranth were observed under this experiment. All the morphological attributes, fresh weight per plant and dry weight per plant were found as maximum for the plants of poultry manure in combination with inorganic NPK fertilizer treated plots and most of the attributes were found as minimum for control. The moisture content was found as maximum for control and minimum for the plants of poultry manure treated plots. The dry matter content was found as maximum for the plants of poultry manure treated plots and minimum for control.

Keywords Organic fertilizer, Inorganic fertilizer, Red amaranth, Yield response

1. Introduction

Red amaranth (*Amaranthus crenatus*) is one of the most popular vegetable crops grown throughout the tropics of the world during spring-summer and kharif seasons. Being a short duration vegetable crop, its growth, yield and quality are largely influenced by the application of fertilizers. Although the organic manures contain plant nutrients in small quantities as compared to the fertilizers, the presence of growth promoting principles like enzymes and hormones, besides plant nutrients make them essential for improvement of soil fertility and productivity [1]. Considering the present area (197,508 ha) and yield (1.371 million tons), the production of vegetables in Bangladesh is inadequate (BBS 2005). Because of cumulative negative nutrient balance the farming system has become unsustainable. A crop production system with high yield targets can't be sustainable unless nutrient inputs to soil are at least balanced against nutrient removal by crops [2]. The use of chemical fertilizers as a supplemental source of nutrients has been steadily increasing but they are not applied in balanced proportion; for example, of the total fertilizer used in the country, urea alone constitutes about 80% [3]. Although chemical fertilizer increases soil fertility, it is doing more harm than good in that the soil itself is being degraded in one hand and the environment is being polluted on the other hand [4]. Moreover, organic matter content in Bangladesh soils is very low, the majority being below the critical level (1.5%), and it gradually depleted by 5 to 36% during the period of 1967-1995. Presently, the yield per unit area of most vegetables is very low in Bangladesh compared to many other countries. In addition, vegetable culture, being of short duration, is generally labor intensive and more number of crops can be taken from unit area. It is suitable for increasing the income of small farmers and it provides one of the most important methods of increasing the amount of food on per hectare basis. Vegetable production also makes more effective use of land and labor resources for agricultural development. Unfortunately, the cultivable land area of Bangladesh (8.3 million ha) is shrinking at least at 1% each year due to non-agricultural uses. Increasing cropping intensity to meet the demands for food for a swelling population has led to mining out the inherent plant nutrients from the crop fields, thereby fertility status of soils severely declined in Bangladesh over the years [5]. Because of cumulative negative nutrient balance the farming system has become unsustainable. A crop production system with high yield targets can't be sustainable unless nutrient inputs to soil are at least balanced against nutrient removal by crops [2]. The use of chemical fertilizers as a supplemental source of nutrients has been steadily increasing but they are not applied in balanced proportion; for example, of the total fertilizer used in the country, urea alone constitutes about 80% [6]. Moreover, organic matter content in Bangladesh soils is very low, the majority being below the critical level (1.5%), and it gradually depleted by 5 to 36% during the period of 1967-1995 [5]. Targeting high yield is the most logical way to raise production from the limited land resources. In accordance of consideration of the above-discussed factors, this study was undertaken to assess the effects of organic and inorganic fertilizers on yield response of red amaranth and to compare the effects of organic and inorganic fertilizer.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Test crop used for the experiment

The profile of the test crop is discussed in Table 1.

Name	Red amaranth
Local name	Lalsak
Variety	Altapeti
Seed Source	BADC
Purity	95% (minimum)
Germination rate	60-70% (minimum)
Seed rate	1 kg ha ⁻¹ (BARI, 2005)
Net. Weight	50 gm

Table 1 Profile of the test crop.

2.2. Land preparation

The land was ploughed several times to obtain a good tilt. Then the land was leveled, weeds were removed and the land was finally prepared before planting seed. Chemical and physical analysis was performed to know the initial soil quality.

2.3. Layout the design of the experiment

The experiment was laid out in Completely Randomized Block Design (CRBD) with three replications. The total numbers of plots were 24. The size of the unit plot was 1.0 m × 1.0 m. Inter block and inter plot spacing were 0.25m and 0.25m, respectively.

2.4. Treatment of the investigation

Eight treatments were conducted in the experiment viz. control; poultry manure; city waste; poultry manure in combination with inorganic N, P, K (NPK) fertilizer; city waste in combination with inorganic NPK fertilizer and cow dung in combination with inorganic NPK fertilizer and only inorganic N, P, K fertilizer (Table 2).

Organic manure	% N	% P	% K
Cow dung	0.4	0.11	0.4
City waste	0.23	0.40	0.245
Poultry manure	1.10	1.0	0.526
Urea	24	0.11	1.20
Murate of potash(MP)	0.876	0.09	32
Triple super phosphate(TSP)	0.012	16	0.16

Table 2 The nutrient content of used fertilizers.

2.5. Application of fertilizers

Organic and inorganic fertilizers were applied as described [7].

2.5.1. Seed rate

The seed required rate was 1 kg ha⁻¹ [8]. Weeding, irrigation, general observations and harvesting were done properly.

2.5.2. Data collection of different attributes

Morphological attributes viz. plant height (cm), no. of leaves per plant, largest leaf length (cm), largest leaf breadth (cm), shoot breadth (cm), shoot length (cm), root length (cm), yield per plot (t/hac) and physiological attributes viz. fresh weight per plant (g), dry weight per plant (g), moisture content (%), dry matter content (%) were recorded.

3. Results

3.1. Morphological attributes of red amaranth

The morphological attributes viz. plant height (PH), no. of leaves per plant (NL), largest leaf length (LLL), largest leaf breadth (LLB), shoot breadth (SB), shoot length (SL), root length (RL), yield per plot (Y/Plot) of red amaranth are presented in Table 3.

Treatment	PH(cm)	NL	LLL(cm)	LLB(cm)	SL(cm)	SB(mm)	RL(cm)	Y/Plot(t/ha)
Control	22e	6c	4.5g	3.17f	15.25e	11e	7.50bc	3.25d
Cow dung	26cde	9ab	5.27de	3.94c	20.40d	14de	5.35e	3.63c
City waste	25de	7bc	4.86f	3.79d	19.60d	19abc	5.15e	3.33d
poultry manure	27cde	9ab	5.56c	4.40b	20.00d	17bcd	6.75cd	4.34b
NPK	29bcd	10a	5.94b	4.70a	21.65c	20.ab	8.10ab	4.45b
Cow dung + NPK	34ab	10a	5.54cd	3.86cd	26.00b	16cd	7.75b	4.95a
City waste + NPK	32abc	9ab	5.20be	3.5e	25.80b	20ab	5.95de	4.25b
Poltrymanure	+36a	11a	6.34a	4.75a	27.25a	22a	9.00a	5.13a
NPK								
CV (%)	9.64	18.69	2.19	1.27	1.71	8.20	6.05	3.311
LSD	6.381	2.801	0.2712	0.1255	0.8638	3.267	0.9644	0.2989
Significance	*	**	*	*	*	*	*	*

Correlation is significant at the 5% level,* Correlation is significant at the 1% level.

Table 3 Morphological attributes of red amaranth.

3.2. Physiological attributes of red amaranth

The physiological attributes viz. fresh weight per plant (FW/Plant), dry weight per plant (DW/Plant), moisture content (MC), dry matter content (DMC) of red amaranth are presented in Table 4.

4. Discussion

All the morphological attributes, fresh weight per plant and dry weight per plant were found as maximum for the plants of poultry manure in combination with inorganic NPK fertilizer treated plots. The dry matter content was found as maximum for the plants of poultry manure treated plots. Most of the attributes were found as minimum for control. The moisture content was found as maximum for control and minimum for the plants of poultry manure treated plots. Without combination, NPK fertilizer shows better effects to increase yield among all the used fertilizers and poultry manure shows better effects to increase yield among the used organic fertilizers.

Treatment	FW/Plant (g)	DW/ Plant (g)	MC (%)	DMC (%)
Control	3.76d	0.28c	92.55a	7.45c
Cow dung	4.75c	0.41b	91.37b	8.63b
City waste	4.96c	0.44b	91.12b	8.88b
poultry manure	4.84c	0.42b	91.32b	8.68b
NPK	5.20b	0.57a	89.03c	10.97a
Cow dung + NPK	5.67a	0.61a	89.24c	10.76a
City waste + NPK	5.70a	0.62a	89.12c	10.88a
Poltrymanure + NPK	5.87a	0.64a	89.09c	10.91a
CV (%)	1.85	5.63	0.25	2.22
LSD	0.2175	0.07249	0.5277	0.4916
Significance	*	*	*	*

** Correlation is significant at the 5% level; b* Correlation is significant at the 1% level.

Table 4 Physiological attributes of red amaranth.

5. Conclusion

Organic fertilizer and organic fertilizer in combination with inorganic fertilizer showed best performance for plant height, root length and other morphological and physiological attributes. The highest yield was found in poultry manure in combination with inorganic fertilizer treated plots. From the above results of the present study, it can be concluded that application of poultry manure in combination with inorganic fertilizer or poultry manure is the best practice among the used organic and inorganic fertilizers.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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